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RESIDENTIAL HOUSES IN SHUSHA ARCHITECTURE HERITAGE

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DZIEDZICTWO ARCHITEKTONICZNE DOMÓW MIESZKALNYCH W SZUSZY

Annotation.

Garabagh, with its capital first in Barda and then Shusha, has always been the cultural, political and economical centre of Azerbaijan. When Panah Ali Khan constructed the Shusha fortress in 1750, its eastern part-Old Shusha started to be built up too. Here Shusha had 17 quarters inhabited by Azerbaijanis. For convenience, they were divided into upper and lower ones. Inhabitants of these quarters used to call themselves proudly galali (living in fortress). The western part of the city, constructed later, was inhabited, basically, by Christians-Armenians, Russian and Georgians.

In Shusha and its surroundings, a considerable quantity of defensive constructions has preserved. These majestic stone monuments of history represent a huge value for researchers. Looking at them, one can understand, at what cost our ancestors always tried to keep their independence. Palaces, caravanserais, bath and apartment houses of Shusha, which have preserved up to the present, bear even more information on history and material culture of the city.

As it is seen, Shusha houses used to be constructed, basically, from stone, with gabled roofs. White and thick stone, which decorated entire Shusha, was extracted in the surroundings of the city and was dressed by local masons. Houses had mostly two or three floors with big windows and beautiful entrances. Most of the houses had also cellars for storage of products and a stable. Many-roomed houses of Garabagh princes, beys and Shusha traders (imaret, malikana), which were quite numerous in Shusha, had luxury and richness. Such houses had big halls for receptions of guests and family celebrations.

Adnotacja.

Karabach, którego stolicą była najpierw Barda, a następnie Szusza, od zawsze stanowił centrum kulturalne, polityczne i gospodarcze Azerbejdżanu. W 1750 roku, kiedy Panah Ali Chan wzniósł twierdzę w Szuszy, rozpoczęto również zabudowę jej wschodniej części – tzw. Starej Szuszy. Miasto obejmowało 17 dzielnic zamieszkałych przez Azerbejdżanów. Dla wygody podzielono je na górne i dolne. Mieszkańcy tych dzielnic z dumą nazywali siebie galali (mieszkańcy twierdzy). Zachodnia część miasta, zbudowana później, była zamieszkała głównie przez chrześcijan – Ormian, Rosjan i Gruzinów.

W Szuszy i jej okolicach zachowała się znaczna liczba budowli obronnych. Te majestatyczne kamienne zabytki historii stanowią ogromną wartość dla badaczy. Przyglądając się im, można zrozumieć, jakim kosztem nasi przodkowie starali się zachować swoją niezależność. Pałace, karawanseraje, łaźnie oraz domy mieszkalne Szuszy, które przetrwały do dziś, dostarczają jeszcze więcej informacji o historii i kulturze materialnej miasta.

Jak widać, domy w Szuszy budowano głównie z kamienia i przykrywano dachami dwuspadowymi. Biały, masywny kamień, który zdobił całe miasto, wydobywano w jego okolicach i obrabiano przez miejscowych rzemieślników. Domy miały najczęściej dwa lub trzy piętra, duże okna oraz ozdobne wejścia. Większość z nich posiadała również piwnice do przechowywania produktów oraz stajnie. Wielopokojowe rezydencje książąt karabaskich, bejów oraz kupców z Szuszy (imaret, malikana), licznie występujące w mieście, wyróżniały się luksusem i bogactwem. W takich domach znajdowały się przestronne sale przeznaczone do przyjmowania gości oraz organizowania uroczystości rodzinnych.

Key words: Shusha, Garabagh, apartment houses, architecture, heritage

Słowa kluczowe: Szusza, Karabach, domy mieszkalne, architektura, dziedzictwo

Introduction

Karabakh, the bearer of Azerbaijan's tangible and intangible heritage, and its center, Shusha, are the most important value for our culture. "The city of Shusha is one of the most important examples of the post-medieval cities of Azerbaijan. The founding of the city of Shusha coincides with the emergence of independent

khanates separated from the Afshar dynasty (F. Khalili, 2022). The history of Old Shusha (before the Soviet rule) can be divided into two main stages, before and after it joined the Russian Empire.

Panahali aga Javanshir, the founder of the Karabakh Khanate, of which capital was first in Barda, then in Shusha, a famous general and statesman, was

born in Karabakh in a well-known family of the Javanshir lineage, served under Nadir Shah Afshar, passed the school of battle strategy and tactics, and learned the basics of public administration here. Nadir Shah accepted him as one of his closest people and gave him the title of "bey". After the murder of Nadir Shah in 1747, independent khanates such as Ganja, Shirvan, Shaki, Guba, Baku and others were formed in Azerbaijan. In Karabakh, Panahali Bey established the Karabakh Khanate by persistently fighting local emirs and maliks who opposed the centralized power. "The Karabakh Baylarbeyliyi, which was founded in 1551, was divided into the Karabakh and Ganja khanates, and the power in the Karabakh khanate passed from the Gajars to the Javanshirs (the Ziyadoglu Qajars continue to rule in the Ganja khanate)" (Chingiz Gajar; 2014)

Panahali Khan turns Bayat Castle, which he built and completed in a short time, into the capital of the Khanate. Later, Panahali Khan built a new capital near present-day Aghdam in a place called Shahbulag and continued to expand the territory of the Karabakh Khanate at the expense of the lands of the neighboring Khanates. The increasingly influential Panahali Khan and Sheki, Ganja, Iravan, Tabriz, Garadag khans were looking for a way to become allies and maintain friendly relations. In order to be sure of the security of his family and treasure, Panahali Khan decided to build a third, this time completely impregnable fortress and move the capital there. It was founded in 1750 in a dense forest surrounded by steep cliffs. "The fortress was initially called "Panahabad" in honor of Panahali Khan, then "Shusha". Architects and builders from all over Azerbaijan were invited to build the walls of the fortress and the city. Residents of the surrounding villages were moved to the new capital. Khan's palaces, mosques, baths were being built. In particular, intensive constructions increased more during the period of Ibrahimkhalil Khan. The construction was led by the prime minister of the Khan, Molla Panah Vagif, who was familiar with construction works very well and performed this work with great love (Chingiz Gajar; 2014).

On May 14, 1805, Karabakh Khan Ibrahimkhalil signed a humiliating treaty with prince Sisianov in the place called Kurakchay, the results of which are still visible today for the people of Karabakh and Azerbaijan. "According to the Kurakchay Treaty, Ibrahimkhalil Khan recognized the authority of the Russian emperor, undertook to pay a tax of eight thousand chervons every year and became a part of Russia. Armenians brought from Iran and Turkey were being settled in Karabakh. As it is known, while the Russians were in the Caucasus, approximately 1.5 million Armenians from different countries of the world were moved to the territory of the former Iravan Khanate alone, and as many Azerbaijanis were forcibly removed from there (Chingiz Gajar; 2014). Thus, with the Kurakchay agreement, the process of rapid Armenianization in Karabakh was started.

The fighting for Karabakh continued without interruption until 1813, when a peace treaty was signed between Iran and Russia in the village of Gulustan. According to this agreement, the Karabakh Khanate, of

which capital is Shusha, fell under the rule of the Russian Empire.

In the order of the commander-in-chief of the Russian troops in the Caucasus, A. Yennolov it was mentioned that, "According to the description of the Karabakh province, in 1823, about 16,000 Azerbaijani and 5,000 Armenian families lived in Karabakh. At the same time, there were 450 Azerbaijani and 150 Armenian villages in Karabakh. There were 5033 Azerbaijani nobles, while there were only 1987 Armenian nobles. Mostly poor Armenians were moved to Karabakh.

Considering that Azerbaijani families are always larger, it turns out that only a quarter of the population in Karabakh and Shusha are Armenians. This is after many Azerbaijani tribes were removed from Karabakh by Nadir Shah Afshar and exiled to Iran.

The social composition of the population of old Shusha was the same as in ordinary Azerbaijani cities. Representatives of the Khan dynasty, gentlemen, clergy, officials, craftsmen, merchants, medical workers (doctors, midwives, chiropractors) and pharmacists of the old, medieval and new formations, teachers of the old and new generation, cultural figures lived in the city.

"According to Russian sources, in terms of the census in Shusha in 1830, the number of artisans increased 10 times, and the number of merchants increased 7.5 times. During that period, the number of bey families (nobles) increased by 40 times. This can be explained by the fact that the landowners in the lower regions of Karabakh had properties in Shusha, where their families lived and which they visited in the summer" (Chingiz Gajar; 2014).

The tradition of Shusha architecture as a unique style in the architectural history of Azerbaijan

"Shusha is a museum-city. It is enough to show just one of the ideas about its architectural monuments - the idea of calling it "Little Paris". The streets, residential houses, caravansaries, mosques, mausoleums and palaces of Shusha have been described by many travelers (Chingiz Gajar; 2014).

Elturan Avalov, the leading expert on architecture of Shusha, divides the construction of the city into three stages. The first stage is the period of laying the foundation of Shusha, building the fortress walls and castles, starting the construction of the lower area of the eastern part and forming the lower quarters. The construction of the upper part of the eastern part of the city and the formation of the upper quarters during Ibrahimkhalil Khan's administration is the second stage (1763-1806). And finally, after the arrival of the Russians in 1805, the third stage resulted in the construction of the upper western part of the city and its intensive development.

In the first stage of the construction of Shusha, Panahali Khan moved the inhabitants of the former capital Shahbulag and surrounding villages to Shusha. The security of the fortress, beautiful natural conditions, and the location of the city at the intersection of major trade routes attracted artisans and merchants from all over Azerbaijan.

Plots of land were distributed to newcomers, and according to Karabakh historian Muhammedali bey Baharli, settlement in Shusha began from the Chukhur quarter located in the lower part of the eastern part of the city. In the initial stages, the construction was carried out in a disorganized manner, without any plan. At that time, black roofs, which were widespread in the lower part of Karabakh and in Ganja were built here. They were cramped and uncomfortable. According to some plan, palaces, mosques and caravansary were built among these houses. After the first people moved to the new place got used to it, the black roofs were replaced by residential houses with their own architecture characteristic of Shusha. There were enough materials and craftsmen for their construction. The massive construction of Shusha began during the reign of Panahali Khan's son Ibrahimkhalil Khan.

Already at the beginning of the 19th century, in Shusha, "the houses were almost all built of stone, most of them were covered with thin, narrow boards, and a kind of planning structure of the city is defined. One of the first fundamental buildings of Shusha, adjacent to the fortress walls and towers, was the palace of Panahali Khan. Its construction began with the laying of the foundation of the castle walls on top of the rock in the region that was later named "Chukhur". Its facade, decorated with an arched alagap, faced Topkhana. To the right of it were stables and farm buildings. Later, Panahali Khan built palaces for his sons with the same materials and in the same style next to his own palace (Chingiz Gajar; 2014).

Despite the outward irregularity of Shusha's initial buildings, it was later divided into distinct neighborhoods like other Azerbaijani cities. Representatives of certain compatriot societies or related professions and one generation settled in these neighborhoods, which differed in size and terrain. In the old (eastern) part of Shusha, as written by Karabakh historian M.Baharly, seventeen neighborhoods were formed. Nine of them were lower neighborhoods, which were Gurdlar, Seyidli, Chukhur (more ancient), Dordlargurdu, Haji Yusifli, Dordchinar, Cholgala, Juhudlar, and eight were upper neighborhoods that can be identified as Merdinli, Saatli, Kocherli, Mamayi, Khojamirjanli, Damirchi, Hamamgabaghi, and Taza. The foundations of urban planning principles of the future city were laid in the old part of Shusha. After the occupation of Shusha by the Russians, the western part of the city, where Christians lived, began to be intensively populated with Russians, Georgians, and especially Armenians.

Streets of Shusha

The famous Russian artist V. Vereshagin, who visited Shusha in 1865, writes about the streets of the city in his travel notes: *It is the capital of the Karabakh Khanate, it is a very well-fortified place. It is protected on two sides by bare rocks and on the other two sides by buildings, walls and towers.*

The city of Shusha is completely different from other cities of Transcaucasia where I have been. Irvan, Nakhchivan and Yelizavetpol, which I visited only shortly, have characteristic features of the East. The houses in these towns are few and low, mostly built

of soil and brick, and are distinguished by their rare windows and low timbers, lost among the greenery of the surrounding gardens. The streets are narrow, littered, crooked, paved with stone or hardly any at all. Shusha is in stark contrast to these cities. The houses of this city are straight, beautiful, high, lit by many windows. It was built from the stones of the steep rocks on which Shusha is located. Big cobblestones are everywhere on the streets. The roofs of the houses are made of thin wood - European style"

At the intersection of the streets, the walls of the fences or houses were built from cut and hewn stones for the convenience of pedestrians and traffic. The streets were very winding, steep, up and down, concave and convex, very winding. As the study of medieval cities surrounded by castle walls shows, such planning of streets that often change their direction and a lot of cul-de-sacs was justified during the defense of the city from the enemy crossing the castle walls.

The pavements of the shopping streets, like most of the other streets of Shusha, were covered with large, rectangular stones and paved with river stones. The outlying streets were in stark contrast to the central streets.

A cobbled arch sewer was laid under the main streets. Shusha is one of the few cities of Azerbaijan with a sewage system. The streets of Shusha were lit by lanterns, and by the end of the 19th century, there were 30 such street lamps in the city.

In the middle of the 19th century, there were 1856 houses, 476 shops, 11 streets, 4 caravansaries, 2 markets, 7 baths, 979 wells, 6 squares, 4 stone and two cobble bridges, 9 mosques and 4 churches in Shusha. Within half a century, the population of Shusha increased dramatically. "Caucaszkij Calendar" (Caucasian Calendar) wrote at the beginning of the 20th century that there were 2,983 houses in Shusha. 2,742 of them were built of stone, 1,191 were covered with iron, 139 with tiles, and 363 with soil. There were 17 mosques, 5 churches, 52 streets, 116 alleys, a city park, 3 hotels, 36 snack bars, 879 craft workshops, and nearly 2,000 merchant shops.

As can be seen from the above-mentioned information, the houses in Shusha were mostly built of stone and covered with inflatable roofs. The white, solid stone that adorns Shusha was quarried on the outskirts of the city and carved by local carpenters. Most of the houses were two or three stories with large windows and very large street doors. Most of them had cellars and barns to store food. There were quite a lot of houses of Karabakh princes, beys and Shusha merchants in the city. The multi-room mansions were distinguished by their splendor and wealth. Such houses had large halls for receiving guests and holding family parties. The walls were decorated with flower ornaments or battle and hunting scenes by skilled craftsmen, as is customary in Azerbaijan. Under the ceiling, alcoves were built around the perimeter of the rooms to store beautiful dishes. There were large niches in the walls where blankets, chests, and carpets were stored. Small shelves were used to store books, a Koran case, pens and writing materials. Large niches were covered with beautiful curtains decorated with patterns, ornaments, or beads. The upper part of the curtains was decorated with a

fringe and a strip of the same material as the decorations on the fabric of the curtain.

Due to the harsh winter season and heavy rainfall in Shusha, the angle of the roofs of the houses was very sharp so that the snow falling on the roof would not weigh down too much. Houses were built according to the approved master plan of the city. The courtyards did not face the street, they were necessarily located behind the house, and from the streets, elegantly built houses could be seen, rather than the courtyards. The windows and doors of all the houses in Shusha faced the street directly. Local marble stones were laid on the streets, and sidewalks were made of large cobblestones for pedestrians. Thus, carriages could move comfortably.

Mansions in the architecture of Shusha and their layout

After the foundation of Shusha was laid as the capital of the fortress city and khanate, as well as a cultural center, architects, nobles, intellectuals, artists, scientists, musicians, teachers and other artists were invited here. As a result of their efforts and love, the intelligentsia gathered here created a new Azerbaijani city, a different society, in an area located in a difficult terrain, which could be compared with European cities. A sufficient number of schools and madrasahs were opened and the city developed a lot in a short period of time. Thus, a large army of intellectuals was formed in Shusha. Young people from Shusha went to Europe to study and ensured the recognition of Azerbaijan there. For this reason, along with national values, European style and values prevailed in the city, from clothing to cuisine. These names did not ignore the architecture of the city.

"As we know, 17 neighborhoods have been built in the city. Each neighborhood had its own square, mosque, spring and hammam. The houses in the city were two and three-story, large-sized, with many large windows and balconies, and were built of local marble. The windows were made in grid style, the distance between the floors was decorated with stone ornaments, and the roof of the house was covered with tiles. Each house had a stone inscription with information on it. This epitaph necessarily contained the Qur'anic verse and, in many cases, the date of construction of the house, the name of the architect and the owner" (Chingiz Gajar; 2014). The houses of old Shusha were mostly of mansion type. All of them had orchards and were surrounded by stone fences. Houses form a kind of street-corridor, their whole walls often faced the street.

German traveler Baron Von Gatschausen wrote about the artistic layout of Shusha residential houses in Shusha in 1843 in the house of Major-General Jafargulu Khan Javanshir, the grandson of the Khan of Karabakh Ibrahimkhalil Khan: "...My companion, Mr. Aderkas, was introduced to him (Jafargulu Khan) in Shusha and was invited to tea by him. He saw here a strange mixture of Eastern and European customs and ways of life. The appearance of the house was no different from the houses of rich Tatars (Azerbaijani) in Shusha. But inside, there was a hall arranged accord-

ing to European comfort, mirrors on the walls, chandeliers on the ceiling, furniture made of expensive red wood in front of the walls, sofas, armchairs, tables, chairs... The walls were wallpapered, decorated with paintings, all the things were European neatness and luxury. The servants were dressed in Tatar clothes and Circassian chokha."

Wall paintings

From ancient times in Azerbaijan, it was accepted to decorate the palaces, residences, hammams, coffee houses and teahouses of partially rich people in Azerbaijan with battle and hunting scenes, flower bouquets with birds perched on them, as well as with geometric patterns. Several palaces in Azerbaijan were famous for their rich wall patterns. The palaces in Tabriz, Shaki, Yerevan, and Baku stand out among them. In the north of Azerbaijan, only the khan's palace in Shaki has survived to this day, and the palace in Yerevan was burned by Armenians at the beginning of the 20th century. Descriptions of the remaining palaces were recorded in the travel notes of travelers, scholars and merchants.

Each Azerbaijani's house had relatively large living rooms, which were always given special attention to their layout. In the design of living rooms in Shusha in the 19th century, in addition to wall patterns, as a rule, stained-glass windows occupying one of the walls - grids, decoratively worked steamers, niches, or wall cabinets with artistically decorated curtains of various kinds, collected for collection, or porcelain included shelves lined with dishes. In addition, the rooms were enlivened colorful Karabakh carpets spread over the entire floor. In Shusha, the production of carpet sets with one main point and four elongated parts around it was widespread.

Shusha was a rich and highly cultured city, and of course there was a secret competition between the owners of mansions - residential houses in the design of interiors. The middle and lower classes, brought up by the high artistic traditions of the society, tried not to be left behind and often painted and colored the walls of the living rooms themselves, or invited masters who agreed to do this work for a relatively low price.

The famous Russian artist V. Vereshagin, who came to Shusha in 1865, later wrote that ornamental compositions, battle scenes and portraits of heroes were painted on the walls and ceilings of the houses of wealthy Shusha residents. He wrote that the wall patterns are distinguished by their rich fantasy, thought out and executed with great taste.

The names of many of the masters who worked on wall paintings in Shusha have survived until our time: Usta Qanbar Karabaghi, his brother Usta Safar, Usta Ganbar's sons Usta Shukur and Usta Javanshir, Usta Abbasgulu, his son Usta Hasan and Usta Karim were among these masters. Some of them participated in the restoration of Shaki Khan's palace built in 1797 in 1902.

In the paintings of the famous Russian artist V. Vereshagin, living rooms of middle-class residents (names not mentioned) are shown. These paintings of the artist are very important for the interior design of

Shusha architecture. The artist made a valuable contribution to the history of the city during his short stay in Shusha. Due to the lack of other research documents and researchers in this field, examples of easel painting in Shusha, Baku, Ordubad, Ganja and other cities were not registered and thus, their details could not be preserved to our time. Fortunately, in 1954, N. Miklashevskaya studied the wall patterns of a number of monuments of Azerbaijan in the 18th-19th centuries, including the four houses of Shusha. Unfortunately, the study was conducted almost 30 years after almost all Shusha mansions and palaces were converted into hospitals, kindergartens, and rest homes, and very little of those beautiful wall patterns remained. Even the black-and-white drawings of Nataliya Miklashevskaya, to whom we are extremely grateful, testify to the high culture of the monumental painting of Shusha artists and the fine taste of the owners of the studied houses (Chingiz Gajar; 2014).

N. Miklashevskaya studied the wall patterns of the houses of the Mehmandarovs, Haji Mammadov, Iskander bay Rustambayev and Safibeyov, only four mansions of Shusha and provided rare information. According to the researcher, the first three houses were built by Usta Ganbar Karabaghi. The paintings in Safibayov's house were painted by an unknown master, whose style is markedly different from the known works. The researcher assumes that this is Master Safar, brother of Master Ganbar. At the same time, N. Miklashevskaya confirms that the wall patterns on the first floor of the Shaki Khan palace and such compositions are repeated by the artist Usta Ganbar Karabaghi in the small room of the Mehmandarovs' house in Shusha.

The researcher wrote that in Azerbaijan, especially in the houses of Shusha, the surface of the walls was divided into certain elements: bulging panels, panel and wall recess.

The more common motifs of wall patterns are plot compositions that include plant plots, depictions of animals and birds, as well as battle scenes, hunting scenes, and scenes from classical literary works. "The coloring of the wall patterns is distinguished by the richness and brightness of their colors, and the harmony of their combination. However, this brightness and the extreme variety of ornamental plots do not create monotony and tastelessness". N. Miklashevskaya studied a small room and a large living room in the Mehmandarovs' house. It is believed that the wall patterns of this house are among the early works of Master Ganbar (80s of the 19th century). Although the paintings in the small room are in bad condition, only the ceiling and the steamer remained in the hall. Some plots of the wall patterns of the first floor of the Shaki Khan palace are simply repeated here. This allows showing all parts of the wall patterns similar to the Shaki patterns of the Mehmandarovs' house. The researcher believes that the wall patterns of the panel in the Mehmandarovs' house are more delicate compared to the wall patterns of the hall on the first floor of Shaki Khan's palace due to the neatness of their work and the subtlety of their colors. Both in the small room and in the hall, there are bulging-shaped vapors covered with dense carvings characteristic of Shusha.

N. Miklashevskaya, who studied the wall patterns of the Mehmandarovs' house, compares the grid covering the entire facade wall of the hall to the grid in Shaki Khan's palace: "*The grid forms a beautiful pattern of stars and frames with its fine, elegant structure in harmony with small colored glass and completes the unique beauty of the room*" (Chingiz Gajar; 2014).

The wall patterns of the houses of Haji Mammadov and Iskandar Bey Rustambayev, which are close to each other, also belong to Usta Ganbar. Iskander Bey worked on Rustambayev's house at the very beginning of the 20th century, shortly before his death. Haji Mammadov's house was built a long time ago, and of course the patterns have not survived very well. In both walls of Iskander Bey Rustambayev's house, which are covered with beam, there are steamers, and wall cabinets are placed next to them. In Haji Mammadov's house, the steam room is in a wall with no cupboards and only beams. The chimneys in both houses are similar to the chimneys in the Mehmandarovs' house.

The wall patterns of Safiyev's house were made by an unknown master. It differs from the wall patterns of the Shaki Khan palace and the houses described above in terms of execution methods. There, the simple paintings depicting four angels standing opposite each other on their knees, most likely indicate the taste of the owner, not the artist. Such scenes were in vogue in coffeehouses, hammams, and the houses of the lower classes of the society.

The absence of battle and hunting scenes in the houses described above, where Usta Ganbar worked, convinces Nataliya Miklashevskaya that even though there was his signature in Shaki Khan's palace, the battle and hunting scenes were not painted by Usta Ganbar, but by his brother Usta Safar. In our opinion, the absence of scenes from the past in the later wall patterns can be explained by the negative attitude of the tsarist administration to the advertisement of the heroic passerby of the peoples in the occupied territories. According to contemporaries, the baths in old Shusha were decorated very brightly and with great imagination, as well as in a banal way. A large part of the wall patterns fell on the facade of the building and the dressing area. Most of the baths were decorated from the inside and outside with scenes of battles, hunting, wrestling of wrestlers, as well as paintings of works by Nizami, Ferdowsi, and other classics of Azerbaijani and Persian literature.

Shebeke in Shusha

The big houses of this city differ from the houses of other Caucasian cities with their renovation and shebeke (network) of stained-glass windows. The paintings of the Russian artist V. Vereshagin are a great proof of this. As can be seen from his works, the carved windows of the Shebeke replaced the entire wall of the room from ceiling to floor, or part of it, depending on the layout of the building. Such windows created a joyful palace mood with matching bright carpets on the floor and wall patterns decorated with multi-colored ornaments. Craftsmanship was well developed in Shusha, and there was no problem finding craftsmen and wood for traditional Shebeke production. Window frames and grids were assembled from standard boards without

nails. One square meter of the window net consisted of 3-5 thousand such boards glued together. The colored glasses formed a 10-12-rayed star in the Shebeke. The selected drawing was repeated symmetrically. The windows went up and down. The structure of the Shebeke was the same as in Shaki. The general appearance of the paintings of the Shebeke art of Shusha is much more elegant and complex than that of the art of Shebeke in Shaki.

There were the remainings of Shebeke art in the houses of Mehmandarovs, Haji Mammadov, Isgandar bey Rustambayov, Zohrabbayovs and others in Shusha.

Chimneys (bukhari) in the houses of Shusha

Houses of the people of Shusha were heated with Bukharis, mangals (usually with very beautiful decorative arrangement), and in poor families, in old times, with ovens. Almost all houses had a Bukhari in at least one room. Bukhari was an indicator of the owner's prosperity and financial status in the houses Shusha and Shaki. There was a secret competition between Shusha nobles for the beauty, size and efficiency of their Bukharis.

Unfortunately, only black and white drawings of these Bukharis have survived to our time. Due to their quality and clarity, the best are the paintings of the Bukhari painted by V. Vereshagin. Unfortunately, he did not mention the names of the owners of the most interesting houses with bukharis.

In her article (1954) related to the wall ornaments of Azerbaijan, N. Miklashevskaya provides interesting information. About the bukhari in the house of the Mehmandarovs, she writes: "Its construction is characteristic for the bukharis of Shusha. Bukhari is built a little bit forward from the line of the wall and it has a four-square shape with a chimney formed extension with the height of a meter and a half. There is small decorative square located above it. Above this square, it is completed with wall paintings of steaming flowers directly on the wall. The firework on the steamer's mirror is framed by a complex ashlar arch. Bukhara is not so richly decorated. The simple geometric plant ornament adorning its well-profiled stripes is a highlight. The wall colors of stylized flowers on a blue background are repeated in the tympanums of the bulging shape of the fireplace, as in the tympanums of the panel of the adjacent room. There is very little bronze color in Bukhari's murals. As already mentioned, the frescoes of the ceiling are well preserved. This cannot be said about Bukhari's wall paintings" (Miklashevskaya; 1952).

The walls of the hall in the house of Iskandar Bey Rustambayev have two identical bukhari, and in the house of Haji Mammadov, there is one. All three bukharis are of the same type: "The bukhari is located in the center of both walls of the hall of Rustambayev's house, which are covered with shalbanbasi, and its wall cabinets are located on the sides."

In Mammadov's house, there is only one chimney in the center of a wall covered with shalbanbasi (to the right of the entrance door). The bukharis of these houses are similar in composition to the bukharis of the hall of the Mehmandarovs' house.

N. Miklashevskaya describes the wall patterns of the bukhari located in the house of Haji Mammadov, where the artist Usta Ganbar worked: "The basic plot of the bukhari's patterns is a pheasant composition surrounded by roses. According to the size, shape and color of the pheasant, it is the same as the other wall patterns of Usta Ganbar.

Mansions

Since the number of wealthy people in Shusha was large, houses were built more luxuriously than others. All of these factors made Shusha a very beautiful city.

The architectural style of a number of houses has been relevant at all times. For example, the entrance door of Jahangir Khan's house (the building where the Shusha District Police Department is located) has a block system. After entering through the gabled front door from the street, one can go up the stairs and enter the rooms. The windows of the house are very close to the floor, they are placed higher than 20 cm from the floor. There is a large gate in the building itself for the entrance of the carriage to the yard. In such houses, even in the 19th century, there was a bathroom in the second and third stages. In order to drain the dirty water, siphon-shaped channels were made in the raft marble stones, which prevented the unpleasant smell from coming from the pipe.

The same words can be said about the palace complexes of Haji Gulu, Khan's daughter Natavan, Bahman Mirza Gajar, Asad Bey, Mehmandarovs and others, as well as the mansions of Haji Dadash, Zohrabbayov and many other houses.

The Mansion of the Mehmandarovs

One of the historical properties located in the city of Shusha is the house of the Mehmandarovs, which is an example of 18th century architecture. The representatives of the Mehmandarov family performed military and political duties in the administration system of the Karabakh Khanate, as well as the whole Azerbaijan. This family is also known for its officials, generals, professors, doctors and many intellectuals. There were officials who performed many duties in the management system of the Azerbaijani khanates. One of those positions was called "Mehmandar". This word is of Persian origin and means "hospitable", "guest loving". The main task of the Mehmandar was to welcome, accommodate, organize food and drinks for official guests, organize their rest at the appropriate level and provide other services. During the rule of Karabakh Khal Ibrahimkhalil Khan Javanshir and his son Mehdigulu Khan, this position was performed by a person named Ali. The name of the Mehmandarov dynasty begins with that person.

The descendants of the Mehmandarovs have been forever written in the history of Azerbaijan not only with dozens of historical figures from this family, but also with the masterpieces of Shusha architecture, the architectural face of the city, the "Building of the Mehmandarovs". The mansion complex of the Mehmandarovs, which is considered a historical-architectural monument of the 18th century, was built by the representatives of the Mehmandarov generation, who

performed many civil and military duties in the administrative system of the Azerbaijani khanates, including the Karabakh khanate. The mansion complex of the Mehmandarovs, located in the Taza quarter of Shusha, includes two large residential houses (one of which has not survived), a small residential house and a mosque. Later, a spring was built on the road leading to the mosque.

When Mirza Ali Bey resigned from his position due to his age, for his special and invaluable services in the development and strengthening of the Karabakh Khanate, Mehdigulu Khan Javanshir, along with many awards, gave him an additional plot of land thirty-five long and thirty arshins wide in a prominent located in well-kept corner of the "Taza quarter". And Mirza Ali Bey decided to build a house for his children in this beautiful place. He wanted to build here an original and beautiful palace with a special architectural appearance, which would stand out from other buildings in the city with its splendor, wealth, in short, external beauty, be worthy of the name of his ancestors, and represent the glory of his honorable generation for years and generations. For this purpose, he invited the famous architect of his time, Karbalai Safikhan Karabakhi, who was the author of several magnificent buildings not only in Karabakh, but also in Transcaucasia and across the Caspian Sea. The master craftsman worked very hard on the project of the building, put a lot of effort into it, and presented it to Mirza Ali. The customer, who understood the construction works well, agreed to start the project, valuing the architect's work.

The construction of the building erected under the personal leadership of Karbalai Safikhan Karabakhi was completed on time. The talented and tasteful professional architect gave the owner a two-story, beautiful, indestructible palace-style private residence made of hewn local stones. With its horse stable, cellar for storing food, kitchen, large hall for family parties and guests, large courtyard, chimney and garden, this mansion was not inferior to the palaces of princes and nobles. Later, auxiliary and farm buildings were added to the building, and it became a fundamental, large residential complex distinguished by its excellence. Thus, a work of art was created in Shusha, which is one of the masterpieces of Karabakh architecture and defines the architectural face of the city. Its name as the "Mansion of the Mehmandarovs" is written to the national history of architecture.

The wall paintings in the interior of the house were made by the master Ganbar Karabagi. Ganbar Rahim Oghlu Karabagi is known in the Middle East as an architect and sculptor. He is the author of various decorative panels and compositions that decorate the interiors of a number of residential houses in Shusha and Shaki.

In the early years of the 20th century, the road leading to the building was called "Mehmandarovs Street". The residential complex of the Mehmandarovs had completely different functions during the years of Soviet rule (since 1930), the district hospital and many other state offices operated here. After its restoration in the eighties of the last century, it became a real treasure of science, culture and art, and this time it opened its

doors to its guests as a carpet museum and began to serve the spiritual world of our people (Guliyev; 2019).

According to the information of the Ministry of Culture regarding the mansion complex of the Mehmandarovs: The mansion complex of the Mehmandarovs was first passported by the Ministry of Culture of the Azerbaijan SSR in 1977-78. The Mehmandarovs' large residential building functioned as the Shusha City Hospital during the Soviet era. On May 19, 1987, the Shusha branch of the State Museum of Azerbaijan Carpet and Folk Applied Art (currently the Azerbaijan National Carpet Museum) started operating in the residential complex that once belonged to the Mehmandarov family. Since the city of Shusha was occupied by the Armenian armed forces in 1992, the exhibits that could be transported in the branch were evacuated and brought to Baku. During the war, the mansion complex of the Mehmandarovs was seriously damaged and destroyed. Most of the buildings on the property were demolished. During the Armenian occupation, the Mehmandarovs' small residential building functioned as the Shusha History Museum.

The mosque on the territory of the complex was appropriated by the Armenians and turned into a Geology Museum. Huge reconstruction works carried out by the Azerbaijani state in our territories liberated from occupation, including the restoration and construction process carried out in Shusha, are executed in accordance with the original architectural style of Shusha. The historical buildings of the city are being restored as part of the works. Currently, the Mehmandarovs' mansion complex is undergoing renovation and restoration. It can be said without hesitation that Mehmandarov's mansion is one of the symbols of Shusha. As you can see, the mansion is not only a residential house, but a complex with a certain history.

One of the most beautiful palaces in Shusha is the palace built by the Karabakh merchant Haji Gulu. Built in 1851, the three-story palace consisted of 46 rooms and 2 large guest halls. The architectural monument was built taking into account national values and the most beautiful traditions of Azerbaijani architecture.

One of the most beautiful estates of the 19th century is the **Bahman Mirza Govanli Qajar** palace complex. This house located in Kocharli neighborhood and other buildings belonging to the complex were in the inventory of the Shusha Rest House until the occupation. Additional buildings were added to this house in the 60s and 70s of the last century. After the occupation, most of the houses were destroyed, and some were completely demolished. The mosque and the fountain of the mosque, located in the Kocharli quarter, were built with the order of Bahman Mirza Qajar and entered the territory of the palace complex.

It should be noted that Field Marshal Bahman Mirza Gajar, the son of Abbas Mirza Gajar Govanli and Assiyeh Khanum, the heir of Azerbaijan and the prince of Iran, was forced to flee to the Caucasus in 1848 as a result of palace quarrels. Bahman Mirza settled in Shusha, moved his harem, children and close people here.

Ker Porter describes the rooms of the palace in Tabriz that belonged to Bahman Mirza's father Abbas

Mirza (the wall paintings of the palace probably belong to the famous Azerbaijani artist Allahverdi Afshar) as follows: "The various shelves on the walls are filled with paintings of old shahs. These paintings are dedicated to their hunting skills, as well as Abbas Mirza's own dangerous hunting episodes. In Iran, the subjects of such entertainment were depicted as fierce as wild animals, just like the objects of hunting. Portraits of beautiful women also found their place in the halls of the palace of this polite prince. The artists of the country use a lot of gold, silver and bright, metallic colors to emphasize the luxury and grandeur of the portraits of the rulers. The portrait itself is a magnificent decoration of the palace walls. In 1739, when Nadir Shah Afshar marched to India, he seized too many jewels from the rich treasury of the Great Mughals. Among them was the famous Peacock Throne, which was set with extremely precious stones on a heavy gold base. These jewels can also be seen in the "Gajar style" portraits painted later, especially in the portraits of Fatali Shah, on his arms, crown, weapon and belt decorated with many emeralds and diamonds.

The house of the palace complex of the famous Azerbaijani poetess **Khurshid Banu Natavan**, daughter of Khan, is considered one of the pearls of Shusha architecture of the 19th century. In the past, a plaque was placed on the building, at the entrance of the house. After the occupation, the inscription on the stone tablet was erased and destroyed by the Armenian invaders in order to fake the history. On the plaque it was written: "Khurshudbanu Natavan, a prominent representative of the 19th century Azerbaijani literature, a smart and cultured daughter of her age, was born in this house and lived and created here (1830-1897). The other house, which is part of the Khan Gizi Palace complex, dates back to the 18th century.

The most eye-catching properties of Shusha's architecture of the 18th century include Husuu Hajiyev's Haji's property located in the Yusifli quarter, Asad Bay's palace complex house, Mashadi Tagi and Yusif Vazir Chamanzaminli's house located on Mir Hasan Vazirov Street, Khan Shushinsky's house located in the Chol Gala quarter, and the houses of the famous Azerbaijani opera singer Bulbul. Most of the houses located in the Haji Yusifli neighborhood were built in the 18th century.

The mansions built in the 19th century, distinguished by their size and rich design such as the mansion of the Zohrabbayovs located in the Gurdlar neighborhood, the mansion of Aslan Garasharov located in the Mamayi neighborhood, Khan Evi (the Khan's house) located in the Kocharli neighborhood, the house of Haji Bashir located in the Mardinli neighborhood (Zulfugar Hajibayov also lived in this house), and the house of Haji Muhammad, Jahangir Khan's house, Haji Alibaba's house (technical vocational school building) located on Ahmed bey Agha oglu street, Hamamgabagi neighborhood, Haji Dadash's house located in Taza neighborhood, Ugurlubayov's mansion located on Karbalayi Safikhan Karabagi street, the house of house Sadigjan, the famous tarzan (tar master) of Azerbaijan, the author of modern Azerbaijani tar, located in Ko-

charli neighborhood, the house of Jafargulu Agha Javanshir and Firudin Bey Kocharli, the house of Jahangir Khan Nuribeyov (the building of the Shusha District Police Department) located on Sadigjan Street and other mansions are examples of high architectural and tasteful design of residential houses in Shusha.

Another famous residence of the 19th century is the house of the Azerbaijani composer Uzeyir Hajibeyov, which later served as a museum. On the entrance of the house, information was written about the birth and living of Uzeyir Hajibeyli and his brother Zulfugar Hajibeyli in this house. The plaque, which was destroyed during the occupation, could not be found. Most of the houses located in Mamayi district were built in the 19th century.

Unfortunately, after the occupation of the city of Shusha, the Armenian aggressors literally razed Shusha, the land of miracles, to the ground without ignoring the demands of international organizations about the inadmissibility of destruction of historical monuments in the occupied territories, with the aim of destroying the evidence confirming that the city was historical part of Azerbaijan.

On September 27, 2020, a great war of honor began in response to the next provocations of Armenian terrorists who were not satisfied with keeping the lands under occupation. The lands occupied by Armenina starting from the beginning of 1988, resorting to all dirty deeds, for 6 years until 1944, were released within 44 days.

In 2022, President Ilham Aliyev declared this year "the year of Shusha" to celebrate the 270th anniversary of the city of Shusha (the city of Shusha was founded in 1752 by Panahali Khan). This event led to the acceleration of works aimed at the restoration of Shusha's architectural monument, as well as the revival of its cultural life and infrastructure.

Conclusion

Some researches believe that, the main purpose of the construction of the five-story buildings built in Shusha during the Soviet era was not to accommodate people, but to demolish historical properties and to lose traces of Azerbaijan in Shusha. As at that time, this policy manifested itself in different forms in all parts of Azerbaijan. Historical-architectural monuments of Shusha city have a unique and irreplaceable place in the history of Azerbaijan. Although it is said that the houses of Shusha are not different from the houses of other regions of Azerbaijan, we think that in Shusha, mainly two-story properties built from local rock stones are quite different. It is possible to differentiate them from residential houses in other regions with their unique construction style and architectural elements. The solution of the entrance portal, which is made of wooden lattice window, glazed balcony, columns, railings and carved stone elements can be the example of this. Unfortunately, most of these buildings have not survived to our time.

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